

REPRODUCTIVE HEALTHY KNING PSYCHOLOGICAL-PEDAGOGICAL
PROBLEMS OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract: Students and students become one of the most vulnerable groups of the population in the conditions of social tension and stratification of society, and a sharp decrease in the standard of living of the population. But exactly students of society reproductive , intellectual , economic , social , political and cultural is a reserve . It's theirs of health huge social importance determines

Key words : student , reproductive health , danger factors , sex education , teenagers .

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ПСИХОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ РЕПРОДУКТИВНОГО
ЗДОРОВЬЯ У БУДУЩИХ ПЕДАГОГОВ

Аннотация: в условиях социальной напряженности и стратификации общества, резкого снижения уровня жизни населения именно студенты и школьники становятся одной из самых уязвимых групп населения. Но именно студенты являются репродуктивным, интеллектуальным, экономическим, социальным, политическим и культурным резервом общества. Это обуславливает огромную социальную значимость их здоровья.

Ключевые слова: студент, репродуктивное здоровье, факторы риска, половое воспитание, подростки.

Introduction: Against the background of changes in the socio-economic and political system in our country, there is a steady trend towards the deterioration of the health indicators of children and adolescents. Thus, statistics show that 50-75% of girls have health disorders that may negatively affect their reproductive functions in the future. We must not forget that the leading factors determining the process of forming the reproductive health of children and students are their living conditions and style. Unfortunately, the socio-economic changes that took place had a negative impact on the change of behavioral stereotypes in the environment of young people - the interest in sports decreased, the necessary knowledge to maintain and strengthen one's health and there are no social motives, while bad habits are widespread, the frequency of premarital sex has increased.

Main part: Many studies have noted disastrous trends in the reproductive health of students, which may be one of the most important causes of low birth rates, high infant mortality rates, pregnancy pathology, and stillbirths in the future. From the point of view of the modern priorities in the field of healthcare implemented in Uzbekistan, the reproductive health of adolescent girls and the problems of preserving their reproductive potential are of particular importance. At present, the activity of the reproductive system of women is undoubtedly determined mainly by its timely and harmonious development in adulthood. However, in the first decade of the 21st century, the reproductive potential of teenage girls in Uzbekistan had stable and mostly negative characteristics, among which the following should be noted:

— reproductive important have has been bad of habits high spread

- physical , sexual and psychosexual in development of deviations big percentage ;
- somatic and gynecological of diseases high level
- enough didn't happen reproductive relationships formation ;
- sexual education and contraceptive low level of activity ;
- abortion main result with a teenager of pregnancy high level Teenagers reproductive to health effect doer the most important factors Dangerous sexual behavior , reproductive system of diseases reproductive , sexual road with contagious diseases , adolescence during pregnancy and abortions , contraception methods according to of knowledge low Sex behavior reproductive health with closely depends in fact his main structural from the parts is one Reproductive health protection to do reproductive health supportive and reproductive function with depends problems prevention get and solution to do through family or of the person well-being which provides factors , methods , procedures and services is a set . of the population illness level and common of death high level of birth decline and children of health deterioration with separate standing modern in the circumstances of the population reproductive health protection to do problems separately importance occupation is doing Family planning family and social aspects have has been health save prevention measures one is the optimal humanitarian to development help will give . Family planning in the program primary medical of help wider to the context attention focus , education bodies , legal and the law issuer organs and public information tools with closely cooperation to do need Family planning services wide comprehensive and cheap information present reach , har one to the person sexual education and the family planning services guaranteed to use provide need Only knowledgeable people responsibility feeling with and own needs , as well as family and of society needs account received without movement to do possible and movement they do. Past in the century sexual of life start of age decline trend observed .

A review of modern foreign and domestic research on this topic shows that the percentage of sexually active young people is increasing, and the average age of first sex is constantly decreasing. Thus, in recent decades, there has been a tendency to lower the age of sexual debut, which reached 14.5 years according to anonymous surveys. In Uzbekistan, the pregnancy rate among teenagers is 70-90 per 1000 people. Abortion accounts for 75 percent of teenage pregnancies, leading to a high rate of pregnancy — about 40 per 1,000 teens aged 15-19. A number of factors influence the sexual activity of adolescents, among which the socio-economic situation, the nature of family relationships, the influence of peers and mass media can be highlighted. However, increased sexual activity is associated with several adolescent risk factors, including unplanned pregnancy, abortion, out-of-wedlock births, sexual exploitation, and maternal mortality. The formation of the foundations for maintaining and strengthening reproductive health, as a rule, begins in adolescence, when the student already has experience in sexual relations and bad habits, which significantly reduces the effectiveness of preventive measures for the formation of sexual culture. At the same time, early initiation of sex education can lead to wrong perception of sexual relations. Research results teens reproductive health said the meaning means the following the results showed . of respondents most of them reproductive health of a person healthy the child pregnant to do and giving birth they believe that it is their ability ; of the body health and of the disease lack of and only one how many answer to give it was hard . Most important social and medical from problems one this sexual road with contagious of diseases increase .

Adolescents' increased risk of developing these diseases is associated with a variety of behavioral, biological, and psychosocial factors, among which sexual activity is considered the

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most important risk factor. It should also be noted that today's school graduates are careless about their health and the health of others, they have a low level of personal importance of health problems, a healthy lifestyle, it was noted that there is insufficient knowledge about the methods of maintaining and strengthening health. Adolescents are anxious and afraid of the changes in puberty and psychological processes that are happening to them. But in addition to complex, sometimes unpredictable characteristics, during adolescence, the desire to know oneself and others, the search for identity, the desire for self-affirmation, the formation and reflection of moral beliefs are important. virtues are formed [3]. With that together, general education of schools modern study plans, for example, reproductive health issues enough attention not given Education of the process all to the fronts effect showed long continue reached organizational and legal changes period, quality education get process more and more difficult being is going on [2]. So so the state education standard according to structured "life safety basics" of the course in programs main at school reproductive health issues from 3 hours, higher in classes 6 hours per year does not exceed That's why for education health storage function only health storage not only teachable, perhaps him study of the process all of participants main the need and marriage style rotate will receive just in case done increases. In children own to health care make it storage and strengthening according to skill and qualifications formation formalized. In practice practice at school this work to lectures reduces their main content clinical appearance, diseases diagnosis and treatment about is information. The rule as, them medicine specialists they read, but they each always healthy behavior teaching and bring up to the methodology of students health storage for positive motivation formation methods have they are not

The structure of interpersonal social support, including the number of relationships and the quality of the person's system of relationships with the immediate environment, in which the family plays an important role, can contribute to or hinder the development of an adolescent's personal preventive resource [1]. From the point of view of modern pedagogy, educational activity is a system of actions (mental and practical), the implementation of which ensures the acquisition of knowledge, acquisition of skills and abilities, and their application in solving various problems. The low level of reproductive health and medical culture of modern students, in turn, determines the need to introduce new programs of sexual education of students into the local school education system, because the current curricula of school courses do not allow students to understand the issues of maintaining and strengthening reproductive health. does not match age characteristics and educational needs. Unfortunately, at present, the level of theoretical knowledge of secondary school students about reproductive health is very low and cannot ensure the maintenance of adolescent reproductive health in practical life and requires qualitative improvement.

Conclusion: Undoubtedly, the strategic priority of state policy in the social sphere should be the formation and development of healthy lifestyle values. The above cases show that the development and implementation of the methodology for the formation of students' knowledge on the maintenance and strengthening of reproductive health as a component of a healthy lifestyle is an urgent pedagogical problem. Accordingly, a new set of tasks will appear in front of educational institutions that require urgent decisions. The most important of them was the development of specific methodological approaches aimed at forming the knowledge of reproductive health among schoolchildren of different ages. At the same time, the modern methodology should help to form a comprehensive system of theoretical knowledge and practical skills of students of secondary educational institutions on maintenance and strengthening of reproductive health. It is based on

the personal interest of students, taking into account the individual and age needs of schoolchildren, wide use of interdisciplinary communication, interactive forms of teaching and modern information technologies, as well as the specific practical direction of knowledge gained about reproductive health. should be.

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